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How are literacy and health literacy (especially HIV/AIDS related knowledge) and HIV/AIDS outcomes correlated in Uzbekistan
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Abstract:

INTRODUCTION: Health literacy is essential to the overall health of the population, and knowledge of HIV and AIDS is essential to preventing its spread. Literacy rates in Central Asia are gradually increasing in Central Asia. Besides Uzbekistan has high literacy rate in the region. Limited data exists to correlate literacy with HIV knowledge in Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan, for example, has a low HIV prevalence rate but is considered to be at high risk for an epidemic because it has low literacy and so on health literacy levels.

AIM: The purpose of this study is to identify associations between literacy and HIV knowledge and HIV Prevalence also that can improve in HIV literacy affect HIV prevalence in Uzbekistan.

METHOD: A literature review was conducted of qualitative analysis designed to assess the outcome between literacy and health literacy as a study variable in the outcomes of HIV/AIDS. Due to the heterogeneity relative to study designs and content analysis approaches among the included studies, I synthesised the study findings rather than conducting a meta-analysis. Content analysis method for qualitative was used to get results for research questions.

RESULTS: After conducting content analysis across 15 studies, it was revealed that a connection exists between literacy and health literacy. Educated individuals tend to have a better understanding of their health, including HIV/AIDS over the time, where knowledge is critical for controlling the prevalence. There is a relation that low literacy rate also correlated with discriminatory attitudes towards HIV positive people. Studies indicate that there has been inadequate progress in promoting literacy in Uzbekistan, coupled with increased health literacy and HIV prevalence rates over the period 2014 to 2024. At the moment, there is no national policy in place in regard to improving health literacy and literacy about HIV/AIDS.

DISCUSSION: The results of this study continue previous research about associations between literacy and health information, while showing its impact on Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSION: The research indicates that a greater focus on education is required to effectively prevent the spread of HIV. Uzbekistan poses a moderate prevalence risk for HIV epidemics due to inadequate level of HIV related illiteracy, intravenous drug use and low levels of knowledge about HIV. In order to identify interventions that can proactively prevent an epidemic, further research is essential.

KEYWORDS: HIV/AIDS, HIV/AIDS outcomes, Literacy/Knowledge, transmission, prevalence.